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Sources:

1. Fortescue, Michael. *West Greenlandic*. London: Croom Helm, 1984.

notes concerning Fortescue's book:

-morpheme boundaries within P- ω marked by "-" or "=" before an enclitic

-potentially misleading phonologic/phonetic symbols:

Fortescue	IPA
g	ɣ
gg	xx
l	l
ll	ɬɬ
rl	rɬ
r	ʁ
rr	XX
rng	nn
ɾ	ɹ
ʂ	ʃ
v	v
vv	ff
rv	rf

-enclitics form one P- ω (under one intonational contour) with the preceding word-form and thus usually fall under the intonational nucleus of the resulting word: *tassa=guuq* (that.is=quote) (p. 1)

Phonology (pp. 333-355)

(p. 333):

-/p/ alternates with /m/ under enclitic sandhi

-/t/ → [ts] / _i and optionally _# (with slight aspiration)

-/t/ alternates with /n/ under enclitic sandhi

-/k/ alternates with /ŋ/ under enclitic sandhi

-/q/ alternates with /n/ under enclitic sandhi

-/q/ → [X, ʁ] / V_V

-/vv/ → [ff]

(p. 334):

-/h/ only in loan words and interjections; and then only word-finally

(p. 335):

-glides [w, j] optionally inserted in the respective contexts: u_V and i_V (not represented in orthography)

-?-epenthesis: word-initially before V

-may also occur after word-final V

-V?V possible at phrase-internal boundaries (p. 338)

-V greatly influenced by following C (especially uvular and/or homosyllabic), but also by previous C

(p.336):

-[n] as non-geminate only found before a vowel-initial clitic:

/q/ → [n] / _=V

-word-final plosives may be unexploded or deleted (especially phrase internally)

(p. 337):

-word-initial C include: all plosives and /s, h, m, n/ (and others in loan words)

-word-initial CC not allowed (except in newer loan words (from Danish))

-word-final CC only as geminate in syncopated exclamations

-word-medial CC only as geminate (except in some loans)

-geminates possible with all C except /j, r, h/

-/tt/ → [tʰ] / _i

-word-final V can be any long or short V or the diphthong /ai/

-word-initial V can be any long or short V

-vowel sequences:

/ia/ → [iːa]

/iu/ → [iːu]

/ua/ → [uːa]

/ui/ → [uːi]

(p. 338):

-more than 2-vowel moras not admitted

-restrictions at word-internal morpheme boundaries:

-may have initial /g, r, l, ŋ, v/ or other CC which are otherwise not allowed word-initially

(see above)

-may have final /g, r/

-canonical syllable type:

(C)V(V)C

where VV is either V: or word-final /ai/

-σ-initial C is obligatory after word-medial V:

-lexical stems usually (C)V((C)C)V(C)

-non-initial morphemes can be either C or ((C)C)V(C) or longer

-syllable-division:

...VCCV... → ...VC_σ||_σCV...

...VCV... → ...V_σ||_σCV...

...VV... → *...V_σ||_σV... (ie: V: never split across two σ)

-all σ-initial CV combinations possible except:

*/ji/

*/i-ja/, */i-ju/, */u-va/, */u-vi/ (where "-" is a σ-boundary)

-/a-ga/ only at morpheme boundary

-all VV combinations possible both word-initially and syllable-initially, except:

*/au/, */ai/, */#iu/, */#ia/

(p. 339):

-all (V)VC combinations possible syllable-finally, except:

*/au/, */ai/

-vowel harmony only in Danish loan words

-all V may be V:

(p. 340):

-geminate fricatives → [-voiced]

-stress doesn't play "any contrastive or demarcative role"

-"pitch is not distinctive"

-intonation only at phrase level to differentiate between sentence types

(p. 344):

-regressive C-assimilation (with a few exceptions for certain morphemes with /t+s/):
C₁+C₂ → C₂C₂ where "+" is a morpheme boundary

-progressive V-assimilation:

/i, u/ → [a] / a_ (except /ai#/)

-lots of affix/morpheme specific gemination, assimilation, coalescence, deletion, and epenthesis rules on pp. 345-355

-there is regular interaction between affixes, clitics, stems

(p. 349):

-metathesis is no longer productive

(p. 355):

-reduplication:

-certain whole affixes can be reduplicated for semantic effects

